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A Bibliometric Solution to the Problem of Translational Science

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Introduction

Bibliometrics has already helped to address the problem of translational science by developing methods for locating any document in the PubMed database in terms of its ‘research level’ (e.g., Narin et al., 1976; Lewison et al., 2004; Weber, 2013; Boyack et al., 2014). This has allowed the University of Michigan Medical School (UMMS) to track the changes in research level of an actor over time. What we have discovered, however, is that actors do not actually appear to change their research level. If a lab does basic research, it stays basic.

This observation has helped us redefine the way we look at translational science. If individual labs tend to occupy relatively stable positions along the translational spectrum, then policy aimed at changing their translational positions is unlikely to succeed. But if we look at the flow of knowledge (from basic to applied), then an analysis of these flows may provide new possibilities for increasing the speed by which ideas from the bench can have an impact at the bedside.

The following builds on the idea that the unit of analysis should be a group of (possibly competing) labs who are working on the same ‘problem’ (we refer to this as a research community). The ‘problem’ is defined by its participants (researchers, funders, commercial firms, hospitals, etc.). We focus on the pathways between these problems. One can think of them as roads between towns. Our approach to improving translational research is to focus on the knowledge peddlers who enjoy traveling from town to town instead of the often more prominent researchers who are trying to build a larger residency in a specific town.

The purpose of this presentation is to describe the bibliometric tools we’ve recently developed that are based on this approach to framing the problem of translational science. The structure of the paper is as follows. Section 1 describes the bibliometric approaches to the quantification of translational research we are currently aware of. Section 2 describes the model we are using to characterize research communities, their level of research, and the input-output flow of knowledge between research communities. Section 3 provides an example of a basic research community on chronic pain. The production, import and export activity of that research community is analyzed. The links to research communities that are

more applied are identified. These links represent existing translational roads that knowledge peddlers are currently travelling.

Section 1: Classification of the Indexed Literature Along the Translational Spectrum

At its core, translation is the process of turning initial scientific observations into interventions that improve health and translational science is the study of this process. Translational research is the attempt to traverse a particular step of the larger translational process (Austin, 2018). Implicit in this definition is a translational axis, at one end of which is basic science and at the other end is ultimate application. The large-scale analysis of translational research requires an algorithmic way of consistently classifying documents along this axis.

Narin, Pinski, and Gee (1976) proposed the first solution to this issue by analyzing 900 biomedical journals, finding that citation patterns between journals were directionally biased. Journals focusing on more basic research tended to be cited by more clinically focused journals but did not tend to cite these more applied journals in return. The authors concluded that these patterns could be used to categorize journals into one of four research levels. An example journal within each of these research levels is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Research levels and exemplars (Narin, et al., 1976)

Research Level	Description	Example Journal
RL1	Clinical Observation	Journal of the American Medical Association
RL2	Clinical Mix	New England Journal of Medicine
RL3	Clinical Investigation	Journal of Clinical Investigation
RL4	Basic Research	Journal of Biological Chemistry

A significant limitation of this approach was that it assumed all papers within a given journal were the same research level and that journals did not change their research level over time. While these assumptions helped to keep the model simple, they reduced its usefulness.

Lewis & Paraje (2004) attempted to overcome some of the limitations of the CHI Research approach by using word lists. For instance, they observed that an article title mentioning animal models such as mice or rats were describing basic research, while titles mentioning patients were clinical. After deriving sets of “basic” and “clinical” words based on RL4 and RL1 journals under Narin’s classification—followed by some manual fine-tuning to identify words with the highest discriminatory power—this approach allowed them to classify individual articles along a continuous scale. Using word lists allowed anyone to calculate the RL of any given biomedical research article, regardless of whether the research level of the article’s journal was previously known.

Boyack et al. (2014) further refined the word-based approach by training a multinomial logistic regression model against the 4000 journals previously classified by Narin et al. Using weighted terms from both article titles and abstracts, they were able to extend the application of research levels beyond biomedicine and across all of science, ultimately classifying over 25 million articles from Scopus.

Recognizing a lack of consensus around translational research definitions at the time, Weber (2013) developed the “Triangle of Biomedicine” within which all PubMed articles could be graphed. The Triangle takes advantage of the National Library of Medicine’s Medical Subject Headings (MeSH), which are assigned to articles within PubMed. It consists of three points:

Human, defined as any MeSH terms under the “Human” and “Person” subtrees; Animal, which are any MeSH terms under the subtree of “Eukaryota” other than humans; and Cells and Molecules, which are terms under the subtrees of “Cells”, “Archaea”, “Bacteria”, “Viruses”, “Molecular Structures”, and “Chemical Processes”. Using this method, Weber’s model could assign article coordinates based on the relative fractions of its MeSH terms. The NIH Office of Portfolio Analysis currently uses this approach in its iCite Translation module (Hutchins, et al., 2019).

Since this original work, Surkis et al. (2016) used the National Institutes of Health Clinical and Translational Science Award (CTSA) network and a sophisticated machine learning approach to better define translational research within biomedicine and operationalize article classification with excellent accuracy. Although their model was developed and evaluated against CTSA-linked publications, it could be applied more generally to all PubMed documents.

Section 2: An Open Source Model of Research Communities

Identifying Research Communities

The document cluster solution we are currently using was created by Boyack et al. (2020) using the PubMed database. The database comprised over 18 million documents from 1996-2019. Boyack used a hybrid combination of similar article scores based on text (and precalculated by the National Library of Medicine) and direct citation links to estimate document-document similarity, and then clustered these documents using the Leiden algorithm to create over 28,000 document clusters (i.e., research communities). Each document cluster can therefore be characterized by document-level metadata and indicators such as research levels.

Whether these document clusters represent sets of competing labs is an unresolved methodological problem. We have addressed this problem by having laboratory heads review different document cluster solutions and provide feedback on whether the cluster solutions (a) represent the underlying knowledge of their lab and (b) identify the labs that they are likely to compete with in submitting a grant. We have also used the bibliographies of 5,500 US Public Health Service (PHS) research proposals submitted by UMMS as a double check on the reasonableness of the document cluster solution.

Tracking Translation

Translation, from the Latin *trans* (across) *latus* (carried or borne), is the “carrying across” of information from one community to another. In the case of research publications, this information takes the form of a citation. An article from one research community that cites an article from another is ‘carrying across’ information from the cited paper to the citing paper—from the cited community to the citing community.

This concept is operationalized in the following way. Assume that an article is assigned to Community A. That article also has 4 references to Community B. Information is being carried from Community B to Community A. The number of articles in Community A that cite at least 4 references to Community B provides an indication of the strength of the translational link from B to A. One can also view this as an import-export relationship. Community A is importing information from B and B is exporting information to A.

Figure 1 illustrates this concept by charting exports from a particular research community within the PubMed model: community 8621. For the reader’s convenience, research

communities will be labelled with a combination of their top phrase and top idiosyncratic phrase. The label for this community is therefore “8621: Chronic pain (Pain-related aversion)”. The study of chronic pain is a research priority for the University of Michigan Medical School (UMMS) and the PubMed model shows that a significant number of publications within this particular community are authored by UMMS faculty.

Figure 1. Export relationships between 8621: Chronic pain (Pain-related aversion) and other research communities

At the center of the radial chart is our community of interest, colored yellow because it is classified within the field of Brain Science. All 28,000 research communities that might be an export partner with 8621: Chronic pain (Pain-related aversion) are located along the outer ring and positioned on this outer circle according to their research field. Those research communities that import knowledge from the community of interest are represented by nodes (the size of the node reflects the number of articles where the export-import relationship can be found). The location of the node represents its research level (closer in is more basic). The research level of the community of interest is represented by a reference line: the blue inner circle. In this case the research level is 3.7, near the basic end of the translational spectrum. Links going out from this inner circle are examples of exports to research communities that are more applied. The chart is filtered to show only export relationships of at least ten distinct links. If we consider only those relationships that traverse a full research level then we are left with five research communities that are dependent upon imports from 8621: Chronic pain (pain-related aversion). Of those five, the path to community 1783: Chronic pain (pain anticipation) is clearly the most frequently traveled.

The stepwise analysis of export relationships can be continued in this way in order to build up a dependency model of the entire translational network. Figure 2 illustrates the concept.

Figure 2. The primary export partner of each community is examined for its primary export partner, and so on. The community of interest at each translational step is more applied than the last, as illustrated by the increased radius of the research level reference line.

In addition to identifying and characterizing the links themselves, one can drill down to identify the authors of the underlying papers. These authors are the “knowledge peddlers” who travel between communities, connecting them through the import and export of information. Institutions, such as UMMS, can use these data to understand the participation of their faculty within the network. Table 2 shows the chain of primary export relationships between five communities, beginning with 8621: Chronic pain (Pain-related aversion).

Table 2. Primary export relationships by research community and UMMS publication activity within each community

Research Community	Research Level	Export Relationship	UMMS Publications
8621: Chronic pain (Pain-related aversion)	3.7	1783	15
1783: Chronic pain (Pain anticipation)	2.8	256	22
256: Fibromyalgia (Impact Questionnaire)	1.8	2277	22
2277: Pain catastrophizing (Pain catastrophizing)	1.6	130	6
130: Pain intensity (Chronic LBP)	1.2		3

UMMS faculty are active at the more basic levels of this translational network but have minimal representation within communities at the more applied end of the spectrum. Evaluating the export relationships between the most applied communities identifies opportunities for institutional intervention.

While each node of the charts above represents a distinct research community, links represent the traffic of micro-solutions between these communities. As towns and villages are connected by roads, research communities are connected by these information trade routes. Examining the traffic of a given route reveals the micro-solutions being exchanged. An understanding of the underlying information exchange that delineates a translational research problem is necessary for effective intervention. In Table 2, there is a sharp drop in UMMS

participation in the translational network after community 256: Fibromyalgia (Impact Questionnaire). If the UMMS wished to increase its activity within this network at more applied levels, then it should not direct additional resources to 2277: Pain catastrophizing (Pain catastrophizing) or 130: Pain intensity (Chronic LBP) directly, or even necessarily hire additional faculty with prominent labs in these communities. Rather, it would be more effective to evaluate the links between community 256:2277 and 2277:130, targeting institutional investments at this narrow intersection between the larger communities. Table 3 uses phrase clouds to identify the information exchanged between these research community pairs.

Table 3. Bi-gram phrases from article abstracts and titles are used to label the information exchanged along particular translational pathway

256:2277 Relationship	2277:130 Relationship
<p>depressive symptoms Adaptive Copers psychological symptoms psychological distress activity pacing cognitive-behavioral therapy positive affect chronic pain Catastrophizing Scale fibromyalgia female patients interpersonally distressed pain-related beliefs fibromyalgia impact physical activity musculoskeletal pain pain intensity coping strategies widespread pain fibromyalgia FM physical function pain catastrophizing</p>	<p>Disability Questionnaire internal consistency fear-avoidance beliefs aerobic fitness pain-related fear back pain Oswestry Disability Index psychological factors emotional distress graded exposure physical activity Tampa Scale Fear-Avoidance Beliefs Questionnaire psychometric properties outcome measures pain intensity pain catastrophizing chronic LBP physical therapy chronic pain musculoskeletal pain depressive symptoms</p>

A global model for community level dependency maps of this kind is the first significant step forward for the field of translational science since the foundation of the National Center for Advancing Translational Science (NCATS) in 2012. The quantitative definition of research communities provided by Boyack et al. (2020) and the public availability of the model ensure that translational scientists, sponsor agencies, and research institutions begin with a common framework and shared vocabulary of measures. Expanding this model to include the links between communities—and the translational pathways these links describe—is a novel foundation for the study of translational science. Further, this paradigm offers sponsor agencies, academic institutions, and other interested parties a practical and highly targeted way of identifying potential problem-focused interventions.

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